
Salient Innovations in the Nigeria Tax Act 2025 And Their Transformative Implications for Business Enterprises and Taxpayers

Excellence C. Owhor, LL. B, BL, AICMC

Abstract

The Nigerian Tax Act 2025 marks one of the most ambitious overhauls of the nation's fiscal framework in decades, signaling a decisive shift toward a modern, transparent, and growth-aligned tax system. Long criticized for its fragmentation, inconsistencies, and obsolete provisions, Nigeria's tax landscape has now been consolidated into a single, coherent statute that aligns with global standards and the realities of a digital economy. Beyond streamlining multiple enactments, the Act introduces groundbreaking reforms in digital asset taxation, international tax rules, capital gains, and nationwide compliance procedures. Together, these innovations aim to strengthen revenue generation, reduce administrative burdens, curb avoidance, and promote fairness for both businesses and individuals. This presentation examines the key innovations embedded in the Nigerian Tax Act 2025, exploring their practical implications, emerging opportunities, and the strategic adjustments required for organizations and taxpayers to navigate this new era of taxation.

Keywords: *Nigerian Tax Act 2025, Tax reform, Digital taxation, Compliance modernization, Revenue growth*

I. Introduction

Taxation has always been at the heart of governance; it is the price we all pay for a functioning society. In Nigeria, however, tax laws have often been described as fragmented, outdated, and difficult to navigate thereby creating loopholes for avoidance and confusion for honest taxpayers. For decades, businesses, professionals, and individuals have clamored for clarity, fairness, and modernization in our tax system. In June

2025, Nigeria answered that call with the enactment of the Tax Reform Acts which is a sweeping reform aimed at enhancing revenue generation, simplifying compliance procedures, and addressing regional disparities in tax administration. This Act does not merely tweak a few rates or add new provisions; it consolidates multiple tax laws into one statute, introduces new rules for digital assets, international taxation, and capital gains, and establishes a modern compliance regime designed for today's global and digital economy. This presentation will highlight the key innovations of the Nigeria Tax Act 2025, and more importantly, unpack their implications for organizations and taxpayers; the opportunities, the challenges, and the steps to be taken to adapt.

II. Salient Innovations in the Nigeria Tax Act 2025

One key Innovation of the Nigerian Tax Act 2025 is the consolidation tax legal framework.

The **NTA**¹ repeals twelve (12) tax laws including the Companies Income Tax Act 2004, Personal Income Tax Act 2004, Capital Gains Tax Act 2004, Value Added Tax Act 2004, Stamp Duties Act 2004 etc. into a unified legal framework for the taxation of income, transactions and instruments and amended sixteen (16) existing tax laws thereby reshaping compliance, enforcement and creating a one-stop legal basis for taxation across Nigeria.

Notably, the NTA repeals the following key legislations:

- Capital Gains Tax Act
- Companies Income Tax Act
- Industrial Development (Income Tax Relief) Act
- Personal Income Tax Act
- Stamp Duties Act
- Value Added Tax Act.

In addition, the NTA repeals certain fiscal provisions contained in other laws, including the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021, the Nigeria Export Processing Zones Act, the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (Establishment, Etc.) Act, 2011, and the Customs, Excise Tariffs, Etc. (Consolidation) Act, among others.

¹ Section 196 of the Nigeria Tax Act, 2025

Highlights of the Innovations introduced by the NTA

1. Expansion of the scope of Income Tax

Income chargeable to tax under the NTA have been expanded to include income from prizes, lottery, winnings, games, honoraria etc. It has also been expanded to include gains from the disposal of property, and gains from transactions in digital or virtual assets (Like Crypto and E-books). **The NTA defines digital assets but does not specifically define virtual assets.**²

Effect: This means that there will no longer be a separate CGT regime, as now, the gains derived from the disposal of property are treated as part of the taxpayer's total profits and will be chargeable at the applicable income tax rate.

2. Updates on tax Deductible expenses

The NTA introduces notable changes to the **criteria for the deductibility of expenses**. Under the previous regime, the WREN test of deductibility required that expenses be *wholly, reasonably, exclusively and necessarily* incurred in the production of income, to qualify for tax deduction. This standard has now been streamlined under the NTA, which provides that expenses must be **wholly and exclusively** incurred for the purpose of generating income. This amendment removes the previously ambiguous elements of the **WREN test**, specifically the terms "*reasonably*" and "*necessarily*," which introduced a level of subjectivity and administrative discretion that often led to interpretive inconsistencies. In contrast, "*wholly*" and "*exclusively*" are more **objective and fact-based criteria**, capable of being measured and verified against clear factual circumstances. This point is further illustrated in **Gulf Oil Company (Nig) Ltd v Federal Board of Inland Revenue**³ where Court of Appeal interpreted the words wholly and exclusively to mean solely and entirely.

Effect: This amendment removes the previously ambiguous elements of the WREN test, specifically the terms "*reasonably*" and "*necessarily*," which introduced a level of subjectivity and administrative discretion that often led to interpretive inconsistencies. In contrast, "*wholly*" and

² Section 202 of the Nigeria Tax Act, 2025

³ (1997) 7 NWLR [pt 514] 698 at p705 para D,

“exclusively” are more **objective and fact-based criteria**, capable of being measured and verified against clear factual circumstances.

3. Revised Exemption Regime on Disposal of Shares

It is noteworthy that the NTA introduces a revised exemption regime for capital gains arising from the disposal of shares. The NTA provides that **gains from the disposal of shares will be exempt from taxation if the disposal proceeds are less than ₦150,000,000 and if the chargeable gains do not exceed ₦10,000,000 in any twelve (12) consecutive months⁴.**

Effect: This represents an expansion of the exemption threshold under the current CGT Act, which granted relief from CGT obligations solely based on a disposal proceeds threshold of ₦100,000,000, without regard to the number of chargeable gains.

4. Implications of Indirect Transfer of Ownership

The NTA also introduces a significant provision that brings gains from the disposal of shares by **non-residents** within the Nigerian tax net. Under this new rule, any gain realised by a **non-resident** person from the sale or transfer of shares shall be treated as a chargeable gain and **subject to tax in Nigeria where the disposal leads to:**

- i.** a change in the ownership structure or group membership of a **Nigerian company; OR**
- ii.** a change in the ownership, title, or interest in any asset located in **Nigeria**

Effect: The implication of the above is that non-residents may face Nigerian tax liabilities on share disposals in a foreign company. Therefore, companies involved in **cross-border M&A or group reorganisations** must assess whether such transactions trigger a Nigerian tax liability.

5. Introduction of Controlled Foreign Corporation rules

The NTA, introduces controlled foreign corporation rules to the Nigerian tax framework. Under the provisions of the NTA, where a Nigerian company controls a foreign subsidiary and this subsidiary does not distribute its profits in a given year, a portion of those profits attributable

⁴ Section 34(1)(a)(i) of the NTA, 2025

to the Nigerian parent company, which could have been distributed without negatively impacting the subsidiary's business, will be treated as distributed for the purposes of income tax in Nigeria, even though no actual dividend has been paid.

Effect: These CFC rules are anti-avoidance measures which aligns Nigeria's tax legislation with international best practices. This provision is in line with *Action 3 of the OECD/G20 Base Erosion and Profit Shifting (BEPS) project*; by bringing certain undistributed profits of controlled foreign entities into the Nigerian tax net, the rules discourage the use of foreign subsidiaries in low-tax jurisdictions to erode the tax base of the parent company's home country.

6. Elimination of Minimum Tax and Introduction of Minimum Effective Tax Rate

The NTA abolished the minimum tax regime previously established under Section 33 of the current CITA and replaced it with a new framework anchored on a minimum Effective Tax Rate (**ETR**) of 15%. This new regime applies to:

- i. Constituent Entities of Multinational Enterprise (MNE) groups; and
- ii. Any company with an aggregate turnover of ₦20,000,000,000 or more in any relevant year of assessment.

Effect: This proposed amendment aligns with the OECD Pillar 2 framework, which establishes a global minimum tax rate of 15% through the Global Anti-Base Erosion (GloBE) Rules, which are designed to counter tax base erosion and ensure that large MNEs pay a fair share of tax in jurisdictions where they operate.

7. Introduction of Rent Relief and Removal of Consolidated Relief Allowance

The consolidated relief allowance scheme under the extant Personal Income Tax Act (PITA) has been abolished by the NTA. In its place, the NTA introduces a new eligible deduction for personal income tax purposes, in the form of a rent relief. This relief is capped at ₦500,000 or 20% of the annual rent paid, whichever is lower. To be eligible for this relief, the taxpayer must accurately declare the actual rent paid and provide any other supporting information as may be prescribed by the tax authority.

Effect: The rent relief being targeted, may not offer relief to a broad number of taxpayers unless when they show evidence of rent paid.

8. Introduction of Partnership of Companies

Under the NTA, where two or more companies conduct business together through a partnership, any income or profit generated from the arrangement will be considered as a source of profits from which each company's share will be taxed separately.

Effect: This provision demands greater reporting obligations from joint ventures and a need for affected businesses to restructure existing arrangements to ensure compliance and manage tax potential exposure.

9. Revision of Personal Income Tax Rates

By virtue of **Section 4 and 12 of the NTA**, all income earned by a resident individual is chargeable to tax, regardless of where it is earned and for non-resident individuals, only income that is derived from or accrued in Nigeria is taxable.

The NTA introduces significant amendments to the PIT rates contained under the PITA, with the most notable reform being the introduction of targeted relief for low-income earners. **Under the Nigerian Tax Act, individuals earning ₦800,000 and below annually are now exempt from personal income tax⁵.**

Effect: eases tax burden for low-income earners.

10. Clarity on the Taxation of Limited Liability Partnerships

The NTA has provided much needed clarity in respect of the tax treatment of Limited Liability Partnerships (**LLPs**). It is to be recalled that following the enactment of the Companies and Allied Matters Act 2020 (**CAMA**), which introduced LLPs, there was ambiguity surrounding their tax treatment due to the absence of corresponding amendments to existing tax laws. In an attempt to address this lacuna, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (**FIRS**) issued an Information Circular on August 14, 2023, interpreting LLPs as companies under the extant CITA, based on their status as corporate entities. However, concerns were raised over the FIRS' authority to do so, as well as the legal foundation of this interpretation, as it lacked explicit statutory backing.

⁵ *Section 58 of the NTA, 2025*

The NTA has now resolved this controversy by explicitly amending the definition of “company” under the Act to include LLPs⁶. The revised definition provides that: “*Company*” means a company or corporation, including a *Limited Liability Partnership*, established under any law in effect in Nigeria or elsewhere.

This amendment removes any ambiguity and affirms that LLPs are to be taxed as companies under Nigerian law. Consequently, LLPs will not benefit from fiscal transparency (as seen in jurisdictions where LLPs are treated as pass-through entities); instead, they will be subject to corporate income tax at the entity level, with additional taxation potentially arising when profits are distributed to partners.

Effect: Given that they are now defined as companies, LLPs will be taxed as a distinct entity from the partners.

III. Challenges & Risks – Nigerian Tax Act (NTA) 2025

1. Complexity of Transition – Businesses may struggle to adapt to consolidated laws and new compliance rules.
2. Technology & Capacity Gaps – Real-time digital reporting and enforcement tools require infrastructure that may not yet be ready.
3. Taxpayer Resistance – Higher effective tax rates eg. The 30 percent for large corporations and broader tax base could trigger avoidance or evasion.
4. Enforcement Inequality – There is this risk that large businesses comply while SMEs slip through gaps.

IV. Recommendations

In view of these changes, companies and individual taxpayers are advised to: -

- Sensitize internal stakeholders through training and workshops.
- Reassess corporate structures and income streams.
- Update tax compliance systems and filing procedures.
- Adopt technology to align with fiscalization and e-invoicing.
- Review contract and pricing structures in light of withholding and indirect tax implications.

⁶Section 203 NTA, 2025

- Engage professional tax and legal advisors to guide the transition and avoid penalties.

V. CONCLUSION

The Nigeria Tax Act 2025 represents a bold step towards a more unified, transparent, and modern tax system. By consolidating fragmented laws, expanding the tax base, and introducing digital compliance, they aim to align Nigeria with global best practices while addressing local challenges. However, these reforms will only succeed if government institutions build the right capacity, businesses embrace compliance, and taxpayers view taxation as a shared responsibility. If implemented with fairness and consistency, these Acts could become a true turning point; fostering sustainable growth, equity, and fiscal justice for Nigeria.